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Research Article

**THE EFFECTS OF RED ONION'S EXTRACT ON OVARIAN
HISTOLOGY OF LABORATORY MICE**Neda Mannani¹, Mehrdad Modaresi^{2*}¹ Department of Biology, Payam e Noor University, Tehran Shargh Center, Tehran, Iran² Department of Physiology, Isfahan (Khorasgan) Branch, Islamic Azad University, Isfahan, Iran**Article Received:** December 2019 **Accepted:** January 2020 **Published:** February 2020**Abstract:**

Onion is a plant from the Aliaceae family with numerous medical uses. Current study was carried out to investigate the effects of red onion extract on ovarian histology of female mice (Balb/C race). Mice were divided into five groups after regulating the sexual cycle (control, placebo and the extract in of 50, 100, 200 mg/kg amounts). The extract was injected intraperitoneally every other day for 20 days. The control group received no medication and the placebo group received only physiological serum. After dissection, the tissue sections of the ovaries were prepared and examined by light microscopy. Results of ovarian histology showed a significant decrease in the number of Graafian follicle in second group, a significant decrease in the number of corpus luteum in second and third groups, a significant decrease in Graafian follicle diameter in first and third groups, and a significant increase in oocyte diameter of second group. According to the results obtained, red onion's extract disrupts folliculogenesis and can reduce fertility dose dependently.

Keywords: Red Onion, Oocyte, Graafian follicle, Folliculogenesis, Corpus Luteum, Mice**Corresponding author:****Mehrdad Modaresi,**Associated Prof., Department of Physiology,
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INTRODUCTION:

The importance of medicinal plants is now more evident than ever and scientists in many countries are trying to identify medicinal plants, their properties, and their effective compounds [1]. Onion (*Allium cepa*), is a biennial plant from Alliaceae family [2]. The most abundant antioxidant of red and yellow onions is Quercetin [3]. Onion phytoestrogens are lignin [4]. Onion juice and its quercetin have been shown to significantly decrease blood glucose levels in diabetic mice but adverse effects on insulin levels in healthy mice were observed [5]. Research has shown that the inhibitory effect of onion extract on fatty acid can induce apoptosis in breast cancer cells [6]. Allium genus vegetables are of the most interesting herbs in restricting cancers that includes garlic, onions, leeks, chives, and shallots. These plants have been exploited in folk medicine because of their beneficial health effects in improving numerous diseases. The phytochemical analysis of various Allium genus members showed that, to date, 16 species have proved potential anticancer properties due to the accumulation of various sulfur and organic compounds like S-allyl mercaptocysteine, quercetin, flavonoids, and ajoene. These compounds with various mechanisms such as hindering cell cycle, inhibiting signaling pathways, inducing apoptosis, and antioxidant activity interfere with diverse stages of formation, growth, differentiation, and metastasis of cancer cells [7]. In a study by Yoko Sakai et al. (2003), it was found that in hypertensive rats, blood pressure was reduced by eating onions. Research has shown that consumption of alcoholic onion extract caused infertility of female rats via negative effects on implantation [8]. Ghasemzadeh (2013) demonstrated in a study that in polycystic ovary syndrome, the onion extract decreased the apoptosis of granulosa cells by

increasing the antioxidant level [9]. Current study was carried out to investigate the effects of red onion extract on ovarian histology of laboratory mice.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

- Test animals

In this study, seven weeks old laboratory mice (Balb/C race) were prepared from the Royan Research Institute of Isfahan. Mice were kept for a week under the normal temperature with free access to water and food. The same conditions persisted during the injection period.

- Treatments

Control group: without any injection

Placebo group: normal saline injections

Three experimental groups: 50,100, and 200mg/kg doses of extract in peritoneum.

To regulate the sexual cycle, mice received 0.5 microgram of cloprostenol injection in peritoneum and three days later, 3 microgram of progesterone was injected under skin. One day after progesterone injection, the extract was injected into all samples. Extract injections were done between 8am and 10am for 20 days every other day. The dissection was performed one day after the last injection and prepared ovaries were studied.

Statistical analysis

Obtained data were analyzed using SPSS program, one-way variance analysis and Duncan test at 5% probability level.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Mean comparison results of various treatment groups using prepared ovarian slides showed significant reduction ($p < 0.05$) in the number of Graafian follicle of second group (100mg/kg) in proportion to the other groups (figure 1).

Figure1. The number of Graafian follicle in all groups

Diameter of Graafian follicle was studied using micrometer eyepiece and showed significant reductions ($p < 0.05$) in first (50mg/kg) and third (200mg/kg) groups (Figure2).

Figure2. Diameter of Graafian follicle in all groups

Mean comparison results of various treatment groups showed significant increase ($p < 0.05$) in oocyte diameter of second group (100mg/kg) in proportion to the other groups (Figure3).

Figure3. Diameter of Oocytes in all groups

The number of corpus luteum showed significant reduction ($p < 0.05$) in second (100mg/kg) third (200mg/kg) groups in proportion to the other groups (Figure4).

Figure4. The number of corpus luteum in all groups

According to results, showed a decrease in the number of Graafian follicle of second group. Adams et al. (1992) reported that progesterone can interfere with ovulation and thus reduce the number of graafian follicle without interfering with FSH levels [10]. Winer (1997) showed that progesterone inhibited nitric oxide synthase (NOS) by affecting nervous system of rat and guinea pig. On the other hand, the use of NOS inhibitors prevents ovulation in rats [11].

Diameter of Graafian follicle was reduced in first and third groups. Leroy et al (2004) found that amount glucose concentration of the follicular fluid was increased by increasing the follicle size. On the other hand, there is a direct relationship between blood sugar and Insulin-like growth factor (IGF-1). Access to this factor is regulated by the IGFBp-1 protein [12].

The synthesis of this protein is controlled by insulin [13]. Other researches have shown that lowering blood sugar and increasing insulin, causes secretion of hunger hormone or leptin which in high levels impedes the development of mature follicles [14]. Another study showed that incomplete folliculogenesis and granulosa cells death was increased in mice with leptin deficient [15].

Considering the above mentioned and the anti-diabetic effect of onion extract and its reducing effect on blood sugar [5], injections of onion extract into healthy mice can be expected to lower blood glucose and subsequently decrease the diameter of the graafian follicle. Oocyte diameter was increased in second group. Follicular fluid is an important environment for the development of oocytes [16] and a certain amount of vitamin C can improve oocyte maturation and fetal quality [17]. Another

study showed that oxidative stress and the adverse effects of reactive oxygen decreased the quality of germ cells [18]. The unchanged number of corpus luteum in first group may be due to the low antioxidant and arginine content of this dose of onion extract.

CONCLUSION:

According to the results of this experiment and the decreasing trend of the number of corpus luteum in second and third groups and also reduced diameter of Graafian follicle in first and third groups, we can conclude that red onion's extract can interfere with ovulation and pregnancy by affecting ovarian tissue at doses of 50, 100, 200 mg/kg.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors contributing to the present study and to this very manuscript have no conflict of interests to declare.

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